

An Open-Source Knowledge Graph Ecosystem for the Life Sciences

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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Supplementary Tables and Figures

Supplementary Table 1. Important Definitions.

Concept	Definition
Database	A data source not represented as an ontology, which can include Linked Open Data, data from experiments, clinical data, and existing networks and knowledge graphs.
Edge	Observed connections between nodes. Edges or triples can also be thought of as node-relation-node statements (e.g., geneA - interacts with - geneB).
Graph	An undirected, unweighted network $G(N, L)$, where N is the set of nodes and L is the set of observed edges between these nodes.
Knowledge Graph	A graph-based data structure representing a variety of heterogeneous entities (i.e., nodes) and multiple types of relationships between them and serving as an abstract framework that is able to infer new knowledge to address a variety of applications and use cases.
Knowledge Model	Within the PheKnowLator Ecosystem, there are two types of Knowledge Models that can be used when constructing a knowledge graph: (i) class-based, in which, KGs are constructed using classes, with database entities connected to the core set of merged ontologies as subclasses of existing ontology classes and (ii) instance-based, in which KGs are constructed using instances, with database entities connected to the core set of merged ontologies as instances of existing ontology classes).
Node	Entities or concepts, which are the subject of a knowledge graph. In the biomedical context, nodes usually represent different kinds of biological entities like genes, proteins or diseases.
PKT Human Disease KG	PheKnowLator Ecosystem benchmark knowledge graphs that represent the molecular mechanisms of human disease.
PKT-KG	Phenotype Knowledge TransLator knowledge graph construction algorithm.
Relation	The relationship that connects two nodes in a triple or edge. Relations are used to specify different types of relationships (e.g., interaction, substance that treats) that can exist between a pair of nodes.
Relation Strategy	Within the PheKnowLator Ecosystem, relations can be modeled in two ways when constructing a knowledge graph: (i) Standard Relations (i.e., a unidirectional edge is used to connect a pair of nodes) and (ii) Inverse Relations (i.e., bidirectional edges created by inferring the inverse of relations from ontologies and implicitly symmetric relations like gene-gene interactions).
Semantic Abstraction	Within the PheKnowLator Ecosystem, the OWL-NETS algorithm is used to decode semantically complex OWL-based KGs into KGs that contain biologically meaningful information. Additionally, the Semantic Abstraction parameter, when used with OWL-NETS, includes functionality that can harmonize a KG to a specific kind of Knowledge Model. See the following link for more information: https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/OWL-NETS-2.0 .

Supplementary Table 2. Acronyms used in the Manuscript.

Concept	Definition
API	Application Programming Interfaces
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest Ontology
CL	Cell Ontology
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible
GB	Gigabyte
GO	Gene Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
KG	Knowledge Graph
Mondo	Mondo Disease Ontology
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PheKnowLator	Phenotype Knowledge Translator
PKT	PheKnowLator
PRO	Protein Ontology
PW	Pathway Ontology
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
RO	Relation Ontology
SO	Sequence Ontology
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
Uberon	Uber-Anatomy Ontology
VO	Vaccine Ontology
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Supplementary Table 3. PheKnowLator Ecosystem Resources.

Resource	URL
Ecosystem Component 1: Knowledge Graph Construction Resources	
GitHub	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator
PyPI	https://pypi.org/project/pkt-kg/
Docker Container	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/Dockerfile
DockerHub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/callahantiff/pheknowlator
GitHub Actions	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/.github/workflows/build-qa.yml
Algorithm Dependencies	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/Dependencies
Dependency Automation Script	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/generates_dependency_documents.py
Testing Suite	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/tree/master/tests
Data Processing Jupyter Notebooks	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/Data_Preparation.ipynb https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/Ontology_Cleaning.ipynb
Ecosystem Component 2: Knowledge Graph Benchmarks	
Human Disease KG Benchmark Details	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/Benchmarks-and-Builds
Human Disease KG Benchmark Builds Archive	Zenodo <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://zenodo.org/communities/pheknowlator-benchmark-human-disease-kg - Monthly Build Archive: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7030039 GitHub <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/Archived-Builds
Human Disease KG Benchmark Builds File Descriptions	https://zenodo.org/records/10065431/files/PheKnowLator_HumanDiseaseKG_Output_FileInformation.xlsx
<i>Knowledge Graph Build Workflow Scripts</i>	
Build Documentation ^a	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds
Docker Containers	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/Dockerfile.phases12 https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/Dockerfile.phase3
GitHub Actions	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/.github/workflows/kg-build-part1.yml https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/.github/workflows/kg-build-part2.yml
Build Requirements	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/build_requirements.txt
Build Utilities	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/build_utilities.py
Build Logging	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/job_monitoring.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/logging.ini
Phase 1 Build Scripts	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/phases1_2_entrpoint.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/build_phase_1.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/data_to_download.txt
Phase 2 Build Scripts	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/phases1_2_entrpoint.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/build_phase_2.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/data_preprocessing.py https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/ontology_cleaning.py
Phase 3 Build Scripts	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/build_phase_3.py

Resource	URL
	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/builds/phase3_log_daemon.py
Ecosystem Component 3: Knowledge Graphs Tools	
Zenodo Community	https://zenodo.org/communities/pheknowlator-ecosystem
Jupyter Notebooks	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/main.ipynb https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/OWLNETS_Example_Application.ipynb https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/RDF_Graph_Processing_Example.ipynb https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/master/notebooks/Tutorials/entity_search/Entity_Search.ipynb
SPARQL Endpoint	http://sparql.pheknowlator.com/ (deprecated 2024) Code to facilitate the hosting of a PheKnowLator KG via a SPARQL Endpoint with custom front end web application and serve data from a Blazegraph triple store are available from GitHub: https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/tree/36fd2d1dad805a58f4a7fb801b2a7c26dfb130a8/builds/deploy/triple-store#readme

³The build documentation provides a detailed description of all of the processes and code needed to generate the knowledge graph builds using Google Cloud Platform resources..

Acronyms: KG (knowledge graph); PKT (PheKnowlator); PKT-KG (PheKnowLator knowledge graph construction software).

Supplementary Table 4. PheKnowLator Ecosystem Evaluation Resources.

Resource	URL
Survey of Open Source KG Construction Software	
GitHub Scraper	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10052113
Survey	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.5790040
PKT Human Disease KGs	
PKT-KG Zenodo Release	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4685943
PyPI Release	https://pypi.org/project/pkt-kg/2.1.0/
Data Source Descriptions	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/May-01%2C-2021
GitHub Actions Workflows	https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/.github/workflows/kg-build-part1.yml https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/.github/workflows/kg-build-part2.yml
Docker	Data Preparation: https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/builds/Dockerfile.phases12 KG Construction: https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/builds/Dockerfile.phase3
Data Sources ^a	data_to_download.txt
PKT-KG Input Dependencies ^a	edge_source_list.txt ontology_source_list.txt resource_info.txt
Build Metadata ^a	downloaded_build_metadata.txt edge_source_metadata.txt ontology_source_metadata.txt preprocessed_build_metadata.txt
Ontology Quality Report ^a	ontology_cleaning_report.txt
Build Logs ^a	pkt_builder_phases12_log.log pkt_build_log.log
Human Disease KG Benchmark Builds Zenodo Archive	<i>Class-based Knowledge Model</i> Standard Relations without Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180774 Standard Relations with Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180772 Inverse Relations without Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180766 Inverse Relations with Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180768 <i>Instance-based Knowledge Model</i> Standard Relations without Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180764 Standard Relations with Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180762 Inverse Relations without Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180758 Inverse Relations with Semantic Abstraction: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8180756 A table describing all files for each build KG type can be found on the Zenodo Community archive: https://zenodo.org/records/10065431/files/PheKnowLator_HumanDiseaseKG_Output_FileInformation.xlsx

^aEach referenced file can be found within each knowledge graph type for every build on Zenodo.

Acronyms: KG (knowledge graph); PKT-KG (PheKnowLator knowledge graph construction algorithm).

Supplementary Table 5. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Methods Survey Criteria.

Criteria	Description	Example Questions
Construction Functionality	An assessment of how well the method covers the steps needed to construct a knowledge graph from downloading and processing data and building edge lists to generating and outputting a KG	Is there functionality to download data? Can multiple types of KGs be constructed? Is preprocessing or filtering performed as part of the construction process?
Maturity	An assessment of the level, stage or development phase of a method	Is a versioning system in place? Have many releases been made? Are procedures in place to enable collaboration?
Availability	An assessment of the openness of a method and the ease of obtaining a copy of the method	Is the method licensed? What type of license is used?
Usability	An assessment of the efforts put in place to ensure that a user, with reasonable technical skills, could use the method	Is there a Wiki, Read the Docs, or GitPage associated with the method? Are there examples of how to use the method?
Reproducibility	An assessment of whether or not the method provides tools or resources to help reproduce the KG construction process and maintain the code base	What tools are provided to help enable reproducibility (e.g., Docker container, Jupyter Notebook, R Markdown)? Does the repository include any form of testing?

Note. The survey questions were adapted from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/aswec.2004.1290484>.

Supplementary Table 6. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Methods.

Method	GitHub Repository ^a	Publication DOI	Primary Goal or Objective (from GitHub) ^b	Method Validation	Most Recent Repository Interaction ^c
Bio2BEL	bio2bel/	10.1101/631812v1	Bio2BEL uses the Biological Expression Language as a common schema for integrating a wide variety of biomedical databases including causal, correlative, and associative relationships between entities on the molecular, process, cellular, systems, and population levels	N/A	Within the last month
Bio2RDF	bio2rdf	10.1016/j.jbi.2008.03.004	Bio2RDF is an open-source project that uses Semantic Web technologies to build and provide the largest network of Linked Data for the Life Sciences	Examined impact of four transcription factors in Parkinson's disease	Within the last week
Bio4J	bio4j/bio4j	10.1101/016758	Bio4j aims to offer a platform for the integration of semantically rich biological data using typed graph models	Tool use demonstration; no formal biological validation	> 1 year
BioGrakn	graknlabs/biograkn	10.1007/978-3-319-61566-0_28	BioGrakn is based on GRAKN.AI, which is a deductive database in the form of a knowledge graph, allowing complex data modelling, verification, scaling, querying and analysis	Illustrative queries spanning precision medicine, text mining, and disease	Within the last month
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	MannLabs/CKG	10.1101/2020.05.09.084897	Clinical Knowledge Graph is a platform with twofold objectives: 1) build a graph database with experimental data and data imported from diverse biomedical databases and 2) automate knowledge discovery making use of all the information contained in the graph	Biomarker studies to demonstrate CKG use for clinical decision-making	Within the last month
COVID-19-Community	covid-19-net/covid-19-community	NA	The COVID-19-Community is a community effort to build a Neo4j knowledge graph that links heterogenous data about COVID-19	Tool use demonstration	Within the last week
Dipper	monarch-initiative/dipper	NA	Dipper is a Python package to generate RDF triples from common scientific resources	Tool use demonstration	Within the last week
Hetionet	hetio/hetionet	10.7554/eLife.26726	Hetionet is a hetnet — network with multiple node and edge (relationship) types — which encodes biology. Hetnet was designed for Project Rephetio	Predicted the probability of treatment for 209,168 compound–disease pairs	Within the last year
iASIS Open Data Graph	tasosnent/Biomedical-Knowledge-Integration	arXiv:1912.08633	iASIS is a framework to automatically retrieve and integrate disease-specific knowledge into an up-to-date semantic graph	Examined use with lung cancer, dementia, and Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy	Within the last 6 months

Method	GitHub Repository ^a	Publication DOI	Primary Goal or Objective (from GitHub) ^b	Method Validation	Most Recent Repository Interaction ^c
KG-COVID-19	Knowledge-Graph-Hub/kg-covid-19	NA	KG-COVID-19 is a flexible framework to ingest, integrate, and remix biomedical data to produce KGs for COVID-19 response. The framework can be applied to other problems in which siloed biomedical data must be quickly integrated for different biomedical research applications, including for future pandemics	Tool use demonstration	Within the last week
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	UCDenver-ccp/kabob	10.1186/s12859-015-0559-3	KaBOB is a knowledge base of semantically integrated data. The system introduces five processes for semantic data integration including making explicit the differences between biomedical concepts and database records, aggregating sets of identifiers denoting the same biomedical concepts across data sources, and using declaratively represented forward-chaining rules to take information that is variably represented in source databases and integrating it into a consistent biomedical representation	Constructed a multi-species KG	Within the last year
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	NCATS-Tangerine/kgx	NA	KGX is a library and set of command line utilities for exchanging Knowledge Graphs that conform to or are aligned to the Biolink Model	Tool use demonstration	Within the last month
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	usc-isi-i2/kgtk/	arXiv:2006.00088	KGTK is a data science-centric toolkit to represent, create, transform, enhance and analyze KGs. KGTK represents graphs in tables and leverages popular libraries developed for data science applications, enabling a wide audience of developers to easily construct KG pipelines for their applications	Demonstrated functionality using Wikidata, DBpedia, and ConceptNet	Within the last week
ProNet	cran/ProNet	NA	ProNet provides functions for biological network construction, visualization and analyses, including topological statistics, functional module clustering, and GO-profiling	Examined H1N1 IAV-human protein-protein interactions	> 1 year
SEmantic Modeling machine (SEMi)	giuseppfutia/semi	10.1016/j.softx.2020.100516	SeMi (SEmantic Modeling machine) is a tool to semi-automatically build large-scale Knowledge Graphs from structured sources such as CSV, JSON, and XML files	Validated using advertising data	Within the last 6 months
PheKnowLator	PheKnowLator	10.1101/2020.04.30.071407	PheKnowLator (Phenotype Knowledge Translator) is a novel framework and fully automated Python 3 library explicitly designed for optimized construction of semantically-rich, large-scale biomedical KGs	Built and compared 12 benchmark KGs including construction performance	Within the last week

^aAll GitHub URLs begin with the following prefix: <https://github.com/>.

^bWhenever possible, descriptions of methods and tools were copied verbatim from the associated GitHub site, documentation, and/or manuscript.

^cThe most recent repository interaction was documented at the time of completing the survey, which was May 2020 (updated in June 2021).

Acronyms: KG (Knowledge Graph).

Supplementary Table 7. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Survey - Functionality.

Method	Download Functionality	Edge list Functionality	Construction Functionality	Multiple KG Types	Other KG Construction Functionality	Process Ontology Data	Process Linked Open Data	Process Experimental Data	Process Clinical Data	Data Processing Limits
Bio2BEL	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	The entire PyBEL ecosystem tools are all available for all graphs generated by Bio2BEL	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Bio2RDF	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Talend RESTful API; community ontology mappings; SPARQL query repository	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Bio4J	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Titan, Anguillos API	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
BioGrakn	No	No	Yes	Yes	Provides different types of API clients (Java, Python, Node.js) and a Grakn Workbase	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data preparation (filtering, imputation, formatting); data analysis (dimensionality reduction, visualization, hypothesis testing)	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
COVID-19-Community	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Neo4J Browser	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Dipper	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	SciGraph RESTful API Build KGs with evidence and provenance	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Hetionet	Yes	No	Yes	No	Neo4J Browser Creates permuted KGs	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
iASIS Open Data Graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Biomedical Harvesters; MedKnow	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
KG-COVID-19	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Leverages BioLink	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Blazegraph	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	KG verified to confirm to the Biolink model, summary statistics	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Data cleaning module, processes other KGs, KG querying modules, summary statistics, node embeddings	No	Yes	No	No	No
ProNet	No	Yes	Yes	No	KG visualization; enables topological analyses	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
SEmantic Modeling machine (SEMi)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Semantic type detector; weighted graph generator; semantic model builder and refiner; link predictor	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
PheKnowLator	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Data download and preprocessing tools; ontology quality control tools; export node metadata; property graphs; SPARQL Endpoint	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No

Note. For scoring, 1 point was awarded for an answer of “Yes” and for the presence of other KG construction functionality.

Acronyms: KG (Knowledge Graph).

Supplementary Table 8. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Survey - Availability.

Method	Open Source	License	Operating Systems	Coding Languages	External Dependencies
Bio2BEL	Yes	MIT	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX, Cloud-based systems and/or architectures	Python, SQL	Bioregistry, PyOBO, Bioversions, various other standard Python packages
Bio2RDF	Yes	MIT Apache 2.0 CC0-1.0	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Java, JavaScript, Shell, OWL	Virtuoso, GIT
Bio4J	No	AGPL-3.0	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX, Cloud-based systems and/or architectures	Java, Scala	Anguillos, AWS EC2/S3, Titan
BioGrakn	No	None	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX, Cloud-based architectures	Python, Java, Node.js	GraknLabs, Maven
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	Yes	MIT	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python	Java SE Runtime, Neo4j, R, Python 3.6
COVID-19-Community	No	MIT	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python, Shell	Neo4J, Anaconda
Dipper	No	BSD-3	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python, TSQL	
Hetionet	Yes	CC0	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python, Shell	Docker, Neo4J
iASiS Open Data Graph	No	Apache 2.0	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python, Java	MongoDB, UMLS, ReVerb, MetaMap, SemRep, YAJL, Neo4J
KG-COVID-19	Yes	BSD-3	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python	KGX, BioLink
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	Yes	GPL	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Groovy, Clojure, Shell	Docker, Maven
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	Yes	BSD-3	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python	Docker, BioLink
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	Yes	MIT	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python	Anaconda, mlr
ProNet	Yes	GPL (>=2)	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	R	BioGrid, GO
SEmantic Modeling machine (SEMi)	Yes	GPL	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX	Python, JavaScript, Shell	Anaconda, Node.js (11.15.0), Java, Maven, Elasticsearch
PheKnowLator	Yes	Apache 2.0	Linux, Windows, Mac OSX, Cloud-based systems and/or architectures	Python, Java, Shell	OWL Tools

Note. For scoring, 1 point was awarded for an answer of “Yes” and for the presence of a license.

Supplementary Table 9. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Survey - Usability.

Method	README	Wiki, Docs, or GitPage	Example Use	Tutorials	Install Tools	Method Use Resources	Sample Data	Handles Different Sized Data	Output Types	Adoption Indicators
Bio2BEL	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	PyPI Maven	None	Yes	Yes	NetworkX, Cytoscape, text files, n-triples, Biological Expression Language, several IO formats	Yes
Bio2RDF	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	None	None	Yes	Yes	Virtuoso dump, OWL, nq	Yes
Bio4J	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	AWS S3	Anguillos API Titan	Yes	Yes	Titan	Yes
BioGrakn	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	None	Grakn Clients	Yes	Yes	Grakn KG output types	Yes
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Docker	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	Neo4j	Yes
COVID-19-Community	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Jupyter Notebook	Jupyter Notebooks	Yes	Yes	Neo4J, CSV	Yes
Dipper	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	PyPI	Jupyter Notebooks	Yes	Yes	TTL, Neo4J, TSV	Yes
Hetionet	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Jupyter Notebook	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	JSON, Neo4J, TSV, and Matrix	Yes
iASIS Open Data Graph	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	None	None	No	Yes	JSON, CSV, Neo4J, MongoDB	Yes
KG-COVID-19	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	None	None	Yes	Yes	RDF, TSV	Yes
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Docker	Docker	Yes	Yes	RDF/XML	Yes
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	PyPI Docker	None	Yes	Yes	OWL or RDF/XML, NetworkX, text files, n-triples files, tar, csv, graphML, TTL, JSON, RQ, RSA	Yes
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	n-triples files, JSON, Neo4J, GML	Yes
ProNet	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	CRAN	R Markdown	Yes	Yes	R data frame object (rda)	No
SEmantic Modeling machine (SEMI)	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	PyPI	None	Yes	Yes	OWL or RDF/XML files, graph, json, TTL	No
PheKnowLator	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	PyPI Jupyter Notebook Docker	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	RDF/XML, NetworkX, a text files, n-triples, JSON	Yes

Note. For scoring, 1 point was awarded for an answer of “Yes” and for the presence of tools to run and install the method.

Supplementary Table 10. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Survey - Maturity.

Method	Multiple Releases	Release Count	Method Published	Collaboration Encouraged	Collaboration Procedures
Bio2BEL	Yes	1	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bio2RDF	Yes	2	Yes	Yes	No
Bio4J	Yes	100	Yes	No	Yes
BioGrakn	Yes	1	Yes	No	No
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	No	0	Yes	Yes	Yes
COVID-19-Community	No	0	No	Yes	Yes
Dipper	Yes	4	No	No	No
Hetionet	No	1	Yes	Yes	No
iASIS Open Data Graph	No	0	Yes	No	No
KG-COVID-19	No	0	No	Yes	Yes
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	No	1	Yes	No	No
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	No	0	No	No	No
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	Yes	3	Yes	Yes	Yes
ProNet	Yes	1	Unclear	No	No
SEmantic Modeling machIne (SEMi)	No	0	Yes	No	No
PheKnowLator	Yes	1	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note. For scoring, 1 point was awarded for an answer of “Yes” and for the presence of at least one release.

Supplementary Table 11. Open-Source Knowledge Graph Construction Survey - Reproducibility.

Method	Reproducibility Tools	Install Services	Deployment Services	Maintainability Measures	Well-Documented Codebase	Actively Used Issue Tracker
Bio2BEL	CLI Tool	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Bio2RDF	None	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Bio4J	AWS S3 Titan distribution	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
BioGrakn	Grakn Tools	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Clinical Knowledge Graph (CKG)	Jupyter Notebook Docker	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
COVID-19-Community	Jupyter Notebooks	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Dipper	Jupyter Notebook	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Hetionet	Jupyter Notebook Docker	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
iASIS Open Data Graph	None	Partial	No	No	Yes	Yes
KG-COVID-19	None	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Knowledge Base Of Biomedicine (KaBOB)	Docker	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Knowledge Graph Exchange (KGX)	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Knowledge Graph Toolkit (KGTK)	Jupyter Notebook Docker	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ProNet	R Markdown	No	No	No	Yes	No
SEmantic Modeling machine (SEMi)	None	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
PheKnowLator	PyPI Docker Jupyter Notebook	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note. For scoring, 1 point was awarded for an answer of “Yes” and for the presence of at least one reproducibility tool.

Supplementary Table 12. PKT Human Disease Knowledge Graph Resources - Ontologies.

Provider	Filename	URLs and Citations	License	Node or Edge Type and Usage
<i>ONTOLOGY RESOURCES</i>				
Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/chebi.owl	URL: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/ Citation: PMID:26467479	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect chemicals to complexes, diseases, genes, GO biological processes, GO cellular components, GO molecular functions, pathways, phenotypes, reactions, and transcripts.
Cell Ontology (CL) ^a	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/uberon/ext.owl	URL: https://github.com/obophenotype/cell-ontology Citation: PMID:27377652	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect transcripts and proteins to cells. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: ChEBI, GO, PATO, PRO, RO, Uberon.
Cell Line Ontology (CLO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/clo.owl	URL: https://obofoundry.org/ontology/clo.html Citation: PMID:25852852	CC BY 3.0	Utilized to map cell lines to transcripts and proteins. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: CL, DOID, NCBITaxon, Uberon.
Gene Ontology (GO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/go.owl	URL: http://geneontology.org/ Citations: PMID:10802651; PMID:36866529	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect biological processes, cellular components, and molecular functions to chemicals, pathways, and proteins. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: CL, NCBITaxon, RO, and Uberon.
Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hp.owl	URL: https://ontology.iax.org/api/hp/docs/ Citation: PMID:33264411	MIT License	Utilized to connect phenotypes to chemicals, diseases, genes, and variants. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: CL, ChEBI, GO, and Uberon.
Mondo Disease Ontology (Mondo)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/mondo.owl	URL: https://mondo.monarchinitiative.org/ Citation: DOI:10.1101/2022.04.13.22273750	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect diseases to chemicals, phenotypes, genes, and variants. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: CL, NCBITaxon, GO, HPO, and Uberon.
Pathway Ontology (PW)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/pw.owl	URL: https://rgd.mcgw.edu/wg/home/pathway2/ Citation: PMID:24499703	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect pathways to GO biological processes, GO cellular components, GO molecular functions, and Reactome pathways.
Protein Ontology (PRO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/pr.owl	URL: https://proconsortium.org/ Citation: PMID:20935045	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect proteins to chemicals, genes, anatomy, catalysts, cell lines, cofactors, complexes, GO biological processes, GO cellular components, GO molecular functions, pathways, proteins, reactions, and transcripts. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: ChEBI, DOID, and GO. The ontology was subset to only include homo sapien proteins.
Relations Ontology (RO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ro.owl	URL: https://github.com/oborel/obo-relations/ Citation: PMID:15892874	CC 1.0 Universal	Utilized this to connect all data sources added to the core set of merged ontologies.
Sequence Ontology (SO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/so.owl	URL: https://github.com/The-Sequence-Ontology/SO-Ontologies Citation: PMID:15892872	CC BY 4.0	Utilized to connect transcripts and other genomic material like genes and variants.
Uber-Anatomy Ontology (Uberon)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/uberon/ext.owl	URL: http://obophenotype.github.io/uberon/ Citation: PMID:22293552; PMID: 25009735	CC BY 3.0	Utilized to connect tissues, fluids, and cells to proteins and transcripts. Additionally, this ontology imports the following ontologies: ChEBI, CL, GO, PRO.
Vaccine Ontology (VO)	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/vo.owl	URL: https://github.com/vaccineontology/VO	CC BY 3.0	Utilized the edges between this ontology and those it

Provider	Filename	URLs and Citations	License	Node or Edge Type and Usage
		Citation: PMID:23256535; PMID:21624163		imports: ChEBI, DOID, GO, PRO, and Uberon.
<i>EDGE SET RESOURCES</i>				
ClinVar	variant_summary.txt	URL: https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pub/clinvar Citation: PMID:29165669	MIT License	variant-gene; variant-disease; variant-phenotype
Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD)	CTD_chemicals_diseases.tsv CTD_chem_gene_ixns.tsv CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv CTD_genes_pathways.tsv	URL: http://ctdbase.org/ Citation: PMID:36169237	CC BY 4.0	chemical-disease; chemical-phenotype chemical-gene; chemical-protein chemical-biological process; chemical-cellular component; chemical-molecular function gene-pathway
DisGeNET	Curated_gene_disease_associations.tsv	URL: https://www.disgenet.org/ Citation: PMID:31680165	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	gene-disease; gene-phenotype
Ensembl	Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.gtf Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.uniprot.tsv.gz Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.entrez.tsv.gz	URL: https://useast.ensembl.org/ Citation: PMID:36318249	Apache 2.0	gene-protein; gene-transcript; transcript-protein
Gene MANIA	COMBINED.DEFAULT_NETWORKS.BP_COMBINI_NG.txt	URL: https://genemania.org/ Citation: PMID:20576703	CC BY 4.0	gene-gene
Gene Ontology	goa_human.gaf	URL: http://geneontology.org/ Citation: PMID:10802651; PMID:36866529	CC BY 4.0	protein-biological process; protein-cellular component; protein-molecular function
The Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) Project	https://storage.googleapis.com/gtex_analysis_v8/rna_seq_data/GTEx_Analysis_2017-06-05_v8_RNASeQCv1.1.9_gene_median_tpm.gct.gz	URL: https://gtexportal.org/home/ Citation: PMID:23715323	CC BY 4.0	protein-anatomy; protein-cell; transcript-anatomy; transcript-cell
HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC)	hgnc_complete_set.txt	URL: https://www.genenames.org/ Citation: PMID:36243972	CCO	gene-protein; gene-transcript; transcript-protein
The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)	phenotype.hpoa	URL: https://hpo.jax.org/ Citation: PMID:33264411	MIT License	disease-phenotype
The Human Protein Atlas	API Query	URL: https://www.proteinatlas.org/ Citation: PubMed:25613900	CC BY 3.0	protein-anatomy; protein-cell; transcript-anatomy; transcript-cell
The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)	Homo_sapiens.gene_info.gz	URL: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/ Citation: PMID:21115458	Terms and Conditions	gene-protein; gene-transcript; transcript-protein
Reactome Pathway Database	ChEBI2Reactome_All_Levels.txt gene_association.reactome UniProt2Reactome_All_Levels.txt	URL: https://reactome.org/ Citation: PMID:34788843	CCO	chemical-pathway biological processes-pathway; pathway-cellular component; pathway-molecular function protein-pathway
The Search Tool for Recurring Instances of	9606.protein.links.v11.0.txt	URL: https://string-db.org/ Citation: PMID:36370105	CC BY 4.0	protein-protein

Provider	Filename	URLs and Citations	License	Node or Edge Type and Usage
Neighbouring Genes (STRING) Database				
Universal Protein Resource (UniProt)	API Query	URL: https://www.uniprot.org/ Citation: PMID:36408920	CC BY 4.0	gene-protein; gene-transcript; transcript-protein protein-catalyst; protein-cofactor
<i>MAPPING AND FILTERING RESOURCES</i>				
Chemical Entities of Biological Interest (ChEBI)	names.tsv	URL: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/ Citation: PMID:26467479	CC BY 4.0	Used in combination with MeSH to obtain mappings between MeSH identifiers and ChEBI identifiers for chemicals-diseases, chemicals-genes, chemical-GO biological processes, chemicals-GO cellular components, chemicals-GO molecular functions, chemicals-phenotypes, chemicals-proteins, and chemicals-transcripts.
Compath	curated_mappings.txt kegg_reactome.csv	URLs: - https://compath.scai.fraunhofer.de/ - https://github.com/ComPath/compath-resources/tree/master/mappings Citation: PMID:30564458	Imprint MIT License	To align Reactome pathway concept identifiers to PW.
DisGeNET	disease_mappings.tsv	URL: https://www.disgenet.org/ Citation: PMID:31680165	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	Obtain mappings between different disease terminologies and vocabularies including: DOID, OMIM, Orphanet, ICD9, ICD10, the UMLS and MeSH to Mondo and the HPO.
The Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)	mesh2021.nt	URL: https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html Citation: PMID:13982385	Terms and Conditions	Used in combination with ChEBI to obtain mappings between MeSH identifiers and ChEBI identifiers for chemicals-diseases, chemicals-genes, chemical-GO biological processes, chemicals-GO cellular components, chemicals-GO molecular functions, chemicals-phenotypes, chemicals-proteins, and chemicals-transcripts.
Protein Ontology (PRO)	pro_mapping.txt	URL: https://proconsortium.org/ Citation: PMID:20935045	CC BY 4.0	To obtain mappings between PRO ontology concepts to other protein, gene, and transcript identifiers from UniProt, Entrez Gene, HGNC,
Universal Protein Resource (UniProt)	API Query	URL: https://www.uniprot.org/ Citation: PMID:36408920	CC BY 4.0	To obtain mappings between PRO ontology concepts to other protein, gene, and transcript identifiers from the PRO, Entrez Gene, HGNC,

Note. Sources are reported for the v.2.1.0 knowledge graphs (built May 2021). The full URLs are provided here:
https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/blob/549e6e1e882e9ea579508ae24a90e64d962deb8c/builds/data_to_download.txt.

^aThe Cell Ontology is included with the extended version of Uberon.

Acronyms: CL (Cell ontology); CLO (Cell Line Ontology); ChEBI (Chemical Entities of Biological Interest); CTD (Comparative Toxicogenomics Database); DOID (Human Disease Ontology); GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE (Google Cloud Storage); GO (Gene Ontology); HGNC (Human Gene Nomenclature Committee); HPO (Human Phenotype Ontology); HPA (Human Protein Atlas); ICD (International Classification of Diseases); MeSH (Medical Subject Headings); Mondo (Mondo Disease Ontology); OMIM (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man); PRO (Protein Ontology); PRO (Protein Ontology); PW (Pathway Ontology); SO (Sequence Ontology); VO (Vaccine Ontology); Uberon (Uber-Anatomy Ontology); UMLS (Unified Medical Language System).

Supplementary Table 13. Application of Data Quality Checks to OBO Foundry Ontologies.

Statistics ^a	CLO	ChEBI	GO	HPO	Mondo	PRO ^b	PW	RO	SO	Uberon	VO	Merged ^c
Pre-Processed Statistics												
Edges	1,387,096	5,264,571	1,425,434	884,999	2,313,343	2,079,356	35,291	7,970	44,655	752,291	86,454	13,746,883
Classes	111,712	156,098	62,237	38,843	55,478	148,243	2,642	116	2,910	28,738	7,089	548,947
Individuals	41	0	0	0	18	0	0	5	0	0	165	195
Object Properties	116	10	9	231	331	12	1	604	50	242	232	847
Annotation Properties	192	37	53	257	119	11	19	106	41	284	97	656
Connected Components	7	1	2	1	1	3	1	3	1	2	5	8
Data Quality Check Errors												
Value Errors	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Identifier Errors	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2
Deprecated Entities	2	18,506	6,430	304	2,305	0	42	11	341	1,570	0	0
Obsolete Entities	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Punning	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
Consistency ^d	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	---
Semantic Heterogeneity	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	7
Identifier Alignment	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	23,624
Post-Processed Statistics												
Edges	1,422,153	5,190,485	1,343,218	885,379	2,277,425	2,079,356	34,901	7,873	41,980	734,768	89,764	13,748,009
Classes	111,696	137,592	55,807	38,530	52,937	148,243	2,600	115	2,569	27,170	7,085	545,259
Individuals	33	0	0	0	17	0	0	5	0	0	165	188
Object Properties	112	10	9	231	330	12	1	594	50	238	232	846
Annotation Properties	187	37	53	257	119	11	19	106	41	284	97	656
Connected Components	7	1	2	1	1	3	1	3	1	2	5	8

Note. The OBO Foundry ontologies reported above apply to the PKT Human Disease KG v2.1.0. The extended version of Uberon used in this graph imports the full version of the Cell Ontology.

^aThe numbers for the ontologies are calculated using the versions of the ontologies which include all imported ontologies referenced by the primary ontology. This means that the counts of classes include all Web Ontology classes used for logical definitions, not only those that are explicitly part of the primary ontology's namespace.

^bThe PRO version references the human (NCBITaxon_9606) subset created for the PheKnowLator ecosystem.

^cMerged represents all of the OBO Foundry ontologies merged into a single ontology.

^dConsistency was evaluated using the ELK reasoner. The reasoner was only applied to individual OBO Foundry ontologies.

Acronyms: OBO (Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies); CLO (Cell Line Ontology); ChEBI (Chemical Entities of Biological Interest); GO (Gene Ontology); HPO (Human Phenotype Ontology); Mondo (Mondo Disease Ontology); PRO (Protein Ontology); PW (Pathway Ontology); RO (Relation Ontology); SO (Sequence Ontology); Uberon (Uber-Anatomy Ontology); VO (Vaccine Ontology).

Supplementary Table 14. PheKnowLator Knowledge Modeling Approaches.

Example: Add <<EDNRB, Causes, ABCD syndrome>> to an ontologically-grounded knowledge graph.

Challenge: EDNRB is not currently represented in an ontology. ABCD syndrome is a class in the Human Phenotype Ontology, and is included in the knowledge graph.

Solution: Gene is a class in the Sequence Ontology and can be used to add EDNRB to the knowledge graph using two different strategies.

Instance-based Knowledge Model (ABox)	Class-based Knowledge Model (TBox)
<p>EDNRB, rdfs:subClassOf, Gene EDNRB, rdf:type, owl:Class</p> <p>UUID1, rdf:type, EDNRB UUID1, rdf:type, owl:NamedIndividual</p> <p>UUID2, rdf:type, ABCD syndrome UUID2, rdf:type, owl:NamedIndividual</p> <p>UUID1, Causes, UUID2</p>	<p>EDNRB, rdfs:subClassOf, Gene EDNRB, rdf:type, owl:Class</p> <p>UUID1, rdfs:subClassOf, EDNRB UUID1, rdfs:subClassOf, UUID2 UUID2, rdf:type, owl:Restriction UUID2, owl:someValuesFrom, ABCD syndrome UUID2, owl:onProperty, Causes</p>

Note. UUID1 and UUID2 are blank nodes or existential variables.¹⁶² Pink highlighting is used for the EDNRB gene instance, yellow highlighting is used for the gene class, and green is used for the ABCD syndrome class.

Acronyms: EDNRB (endothelin receptor type B); OWL (Web Ontology Language); RDF (Resource Description Framework); RDFS (Resource Description Framework Syntax).

Supplementary Figure 1. Human Disease Mechanism Graph Knowledge Representation.

This figure illustrates the knowledge representation used to construct the human disease mechanisms knowledge graphs. The purple box represents experimental data and the blue box contains the molecular mechanisms created by integrating Open Biological and Biomedical (OBO) Foundry ontologies (gold and green). Edges between the ontologies are created by integrating other data sources that are not part of an OBO Foundry ontology (solid black lines). Dashed lines represent relationships that are inferred from the Relation Ontology and dotted lines represent relationships that exist between imported ontologies.

Supplementary Figure 2. PKT Human Disease Knowledge Graph Construction - Computational Performance.

This figure illustrates the (A) log runtime and (B) log max memory use (GB) performance for each build step with respect to the different build parameterizations or benchmarks provided by the PheKnowLator ecosystem. The ecosystem enables users to fully customize KGs generated by the Graph Construction build step through the following parameters: knowledge model (i.e., complex graphs constructed using class- or instance-based knowledge models), relation strategy (i.e., standard directed relations or inverse bidirectional relations), and semantic abstraction (i.e., transformation of complex graphs into hybrid graphs). The Data Download and Edge List Creation steps are the same regardless of how the Graph Construction step is parameterized. Computational performance was determined using an unreleased build (April 11, 2021) while testing the v.2.1 release

 Findable	Unique Persistent Identifiers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data: Original and processed data • Metadata: Logs and quality reports • Infrastructure: Compute and containers
 Accessible	Publicly Available <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage: RESTful access to builds • Builds: Versioned on Docker Hub • Notebooks: User-friendly examples
 Interoperable	Standardized Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data: Ontology alignment • Metadata: Provenance reporting • Output: Standard file formats
 Reusable	Detailed Documentation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Releases: Code, data, builds • Versioning: Semantic versioning • Licensing: Internal/external resources

Supplementary Figure 3. The PheKnowLator Ecosystem on FAIR Principles.

The PheKnowLator Ecosystem is built on the FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.¹³ Findability. Use of unique persistent identifiers for all downloaded and processed data, Docker containers, and compute instances and generation of metadata, reports, and logs. Accessibility. All resources are accessible via RESTful API access to a dedicated Google Cloud Storage Bucket (pre-2024) or Zenodo Archive (2024), all builds are versioned, and Jupyter Notebooks are used to improve the usability of the Ecosystem resources. Interoperability. Built on Semantic Web standards, grounded in Open Biological and Biomedical Foundry ontologies, and adoption of standard identifiers for all resources. Reusability. Builds are automated, containerized, and deployed through GitHub Actions workflows, resources, scripts, and workflows are versioned using Semantic Versioning, the Ecosystem is licensed, and licensing constraints are enforced for all ingested data.

Supplementary Documents

Knowledge Graph Build Output Metadata

This section provides examples of the metadata files that are output by the ecosystem for each constructed knowledge graph. All of the example files were pulled from the most recent PKT Human Disease KG build, generated on November 1, 2021. For additional details on this build, please see the associated GitHub wiki: <https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator/wiki/November-01%2C-2021>. The logs included in this section are for the class-based + standard relations + OWL-NETS knowledge graph type from this build.

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Supplementary Document 1. downloaded_build_metadata.txt.

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Mon Nov 01 01:45:15 UTC 2021
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DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hp.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 84212277

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/hp_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/go.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 132081899

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/go_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/mondo.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 235314739

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/mondo_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/vo.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8110267

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/vo_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/chebi.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 651338784

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/chebi_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/uberon/ext.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 65910831

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ext_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/clo.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 119273027

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/clo_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/pr.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1223936557

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pr_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/so.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 5225970

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/so_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/pw.owl>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4965358

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pw_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ro.owl>

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 867789

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ro_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = http://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/genenames/hgnc/tsv/hgnc_complete_set.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 15972451

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/hgnc_complete_set.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = ftp://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-102/gtf/homo_sapiens/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.gtf.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1280942256

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.gtf

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = ftp://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-102/tsv/homo_sapiens/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.uniprot.tsv.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 13485382

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.uniprot.tsv

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = ftp://ftp.ensembl.org/pub/release-102/tsv/homo_sapiens/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.entrez.tsv.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 17055479

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/Homo_sapiens.GRCh38.102.entrez.tsv

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL =

[https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/?query=&fil=organism%3A%22Homo%20sapiens%20\(Human\)%20%5B9606%5D%22&columns=id%2Creviewed%2Cdatabase\(GeneID\)%2Cdatabase\(Ensembl\)%2Cdatabase\(HGNC\)%2Cgenes\(ALTERNATIVE\)%2Cgenes\(PREFERRED\)&format=tab](https://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/?query=&fil=organism%3A%22Homo%20sapiens%20(Human)%20%5B9606%5D%22&columns=id%2Creviewed%2Cdatabase(GeneID)%2Cdatabase(Ensembl)%2Cdatabase(HGNC)%2Cgenes(ALTERNATIVE)%2Cgenes(PREFERRED)&format=tab)

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8759737

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/uniprot_identifier_mapping.tab

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = ftp://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/gene/GENE_INFO/Mammalia/Homo_sapiens.gene_info.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 13909469

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/Homo_sapiens.gene_info

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <https://proconsortium.org/download/current/promapping.txt>

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 15271039

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/promapping.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <ftp://nlmpubs.nlm.nih.gov/online/mesh/rdf/2021/mesh2021.nt>

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1948657299

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/mesh2021.nt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = ftp://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/pub/databases/chebi/Flat_file_tab_delimited/names.tsv.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 30365252

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/names.tsv

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://www.disgenet.org/static/disgenet_ap1/files/downloads/disease_mappings.tsv.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 18367848
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/disease_mappings.tsv

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL=

https://www.proteinatlas.org/api/search_download.php?search=&columns=g,eg,up,pe,rnatsm,rnaclsm,rnacasm,rnabrsrm,rnabscsm,rnabslsm,scl,t_RNA_adipose_tissue,t_RNA_adrenal_gland,t_RNA_amygdala,t_RNA_appendix,t_RNA_basal_ganglia,t_RNA_bone_marrow,t_RNA_breast,t_RNA_cerebellum,t_RNA_cerebral_cortex,t_RNA_cervix,_uterine,t_RNA_colon,t_RNA_corpus_callosum,t_RNA_ductus_deferens,t_RNA_duodenum,t_RNA_endometrium_1,t_RNA_epididymis,t_RNA_esophagus,t_RNA_fallopian_tube,t_RNA_gallbladder,t_RNA_heart_muscle,t_RNA_hippocampal_formation,t_RNA_hypothalamus,t_RNA_kidney,t_RNA_liver,t_RNA_lung,t_RNA_lymph_node,t_RNA_midbrain,t_RNA_olfactory_region,t_RNA_ovary,t_RNA_pancreas,t_RNA_parathyroid_gland,t_RNA_pituitary_gland,t_RNA_placenta,t_RNA_pons_and_medulla,t_RNA_prostate,t_RNA_rectum,t_RNA_retina,t_RNA_salivary_gland,t_RNA_seminal_vesicle,t_RNA_skeletal_muscle,t_RNA_skin_1,t_RNA_small_intestine,t_RNA_smooth_muscle,t_RNA_spinal_cord,t_RNA_spleen,t_RNA_stomach_1,t_RNA_testis,t_RNA_thalamus,t_RNA_thymus,t_RNA_thyroid_gland,t_RNA_tongue,t_RNA_tonsil,t_RNA_urinary_bladder,t_RNA_vagina,t_RNA_B-cells,t_RNA_dendritic_cells,t_RNA_granulocytes,t_RNA_monocytes,t_RNA_NK-cells,t_RNA_T-cells,t_RNA_total_PBMC,cell_RNA_A-431,cell_RNA_A549,cell_RNA_AF22,cell_RNA_AN3-CA,cell_RNA_ASC_diff,cell_RNA_ASC_TERT1,cell_RNA_BEWO,cell_RNA_BJ,cell_RNA_BJ_hTERT+,cell_RNA_BJ_hTERT+_SV40_Large_T+,cell_RNA_BJ_hTERT+_SV40_Large_T+_RasG12V,cell_RNA_CACO-2,cell_RNA_CAPAN-2,cell_RNA_Daudi,cell_RNA_EFO-21,cell_RNA_FHDF/TERT166,cell_RNA_HaCaT,cell_RNA_HAP1,cell_RNA_HBEC3-KT,cell_RNA_HBF_TERT88,cell_RNA_HDLM-2,cell_RNA_HEK_293,cell_RNA_HEL,cell_RNA_HeLa,cell_RNA_Hep_G2,cell_RNA_HHStec,cell_RNA_HL-60,cell_RNA_HMC-1,cell_RNA_HSkMC,cell_RNA_hTCEpi,cell_RNA_hTEC/SVTER24-B,cell_RNA_hTERT-HME1,cell_RNA_HUVEC_TERT2,cell_RNA_K562,cell_RNA_Karpas-707,cell_RNA_LHCN-M2,cell_RNA_MCF7,cell_RNA_MOLT-4,cell_RNA_NB-4,cell_RNA_NTERA-2,cell_RNA_PC-3,cell_RNA_REH,cell_RNA_RH-30,cell_RNA_RPMI-8226,cell_RNA_RPTEC_TERT1,cell_RNA_RT4,cell_RNA_SCLC-21H,cell_RNA_SH-SY5Y,cell_RNA_SiHa,cell_RNA_SK-BR-3,cell_RNA_SK-MEL-30,cell_RNA_T-47d,cell_RNA_THP-1,cell_RNA_TIME,cell_RNA_U-138_MG,cell_RNA_U-2_OS,cell_RNA_U-251_MG,cell_RNA_U-266/70,cell_RNA_U-266/84,cell_RNA_U-698,cell_RNA_U-87_MG,cell_RNA_U-937,cell_RNA_WM-115,blood_RNA_basophil,blood_RNA_classical_monocyte,blood_RNA_eosinophil,blood_RNA_gdT-cell,blood_RNA_intermediate_monocyte,blood_RNA_MAIT_T-cell,blood_RNA_memory_B-cell,blood_RNA_memory_CD4_T-cell,blood_RNA_memory_CD8_T-cell,blood_RNA_myeloid_DC,blood_RNA_naive_B-cell,blood_RNA_naive_CD4_T-cell,blood_RNA_naive_CD8_T-cell,blood_RNA_neutrophil,blood_RNA_NK-cell,blood_RNA_non-classical_monocyte,blood_RNA_plasmacytoid_DC,blood_RNA_T-reg,blood_RNA_total_PBMC,brain_RNA_amygdala,brain_RNA_basal_ganglia,brain_RNA_cerebellum,brain_RNA_cerebral_cortex,brain_RNA_hippocampal_formation,brain_RNA_hypothalamus,brain_RNA_midbrain,brain_RNA_olfactory_region,brain_RNA_pons_and_medulla,brain_RNA_thalamus&format=tsv

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 15328159

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/proteinatlas_search.tsv

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/gtex_analysis_v8/rna_seq_data/GTEX_Analysis_2017-06-05_v8_RNASeQCv1.1.9_gene_median_tpm.gct.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 17780477

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL= https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/GTEX_Analysis_2017-06-05_v8_RNASeQCv1.1.9_gene_median_tpm.gct

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://reactome.org/download/current/ReactomePathways.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1423494

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ReactomePathways.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://reactome.org/download/current/gene_association.reactome.gz

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11955743

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/gene_association.reactome

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://reactome.org/download/current/ChEBI2Reactome_All_Levels.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 30485396

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ChEBI2Reactome_All_Levels.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = http://compath.scai.fraunhofer.de/export_mappings

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 196388

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL= https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/compath_canonical_pathway_mappings.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ComPath/resources/master/mappings/kegg_reactome.csv

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 92309

- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/kegg_reactome.csv

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/curated_data/genomic_sequence_ontology_mappings.xlsx

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20641

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL= https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/genomic_sequence_ontology_mappings.xlsx

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8192661
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_genes_pathways.tsv

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://reactome.org/download/current/gene_association.reactome.gz
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11955743
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/gene_association.reactome

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = http://current.geneontology.org/annotations/goa_human.gaf.gz
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 109325311
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/goa_human.gaf

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://reactome.org/download/current/UniProt2Reactome_All_Levels.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 102191227
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/UniProt2Reactome_All_Levels.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = <https://stringdb-static.org/download/protein.links.v11.0/9606.protein.links.v11.0.txt.gz>
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 540934917
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/9606.protein.links.v11.0.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/curated_data/genomic_typing_dict.pkl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 2268
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/genomic_typing_dict.pkl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/curated_data/zooma_tissue_cell_mapping_04JAN2020.xlsx
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 18225305
GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/zooma_tissue_cell_mapping_04JAN2020.xlsx

Supplementary Document 2. preprocessed_build_metadata.txt

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Mon Nov 01 10:00:03 UTC 2021
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DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3662353455

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/DISEASE_MONDO_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3871799

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/DISEASE_MONDO_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3564948

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_PROTEIN_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 2931638

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_PROTEIN_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ENTREZ_GENE_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 15146432

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENTREZ_GENE_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ENTREZ_GENE_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1124944

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENTREZ_GENE_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/GENE_SYMBOL_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 19365937

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/GENE_SYMBOL_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20611429

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8222

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/HPA_tissues.txt

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1530

GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_tissues.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4602
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/INVERSE_RELATIONS.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 358052
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/Merged_gene_rna_protein_identifiers.pkl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 539048900
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/Merged_gene_rna_protein_identifiers.pkl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/PHENOTYPE_HPO_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 719692
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/PHENOTYPE_HPO_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/PheKnowLator_MergedOntologies.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1450356910
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/PheKnowLator_MergedOntologies.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/REACTOME_PW_GO_MAPPINGS.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 398373
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/REACTOME_PW_GO_MAPPINGS.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/RELATIONS_LABELS.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 45000
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/RELATIONS_LABELS.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/SO_GENE_TRANSCRIPT_VARIANT_TYPE_MAPPING.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 28069897
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/SO_GENE_TRANSCRIPT_VARIANT_TYPE_MAPPING.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/STRING_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1326141
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/STRING_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3736130
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_CATALYST.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1639479
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_CATALYST.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_COFACTOR.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 179314
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_COFACTOR.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/chebi_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 643473711
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/chebi_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/clo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 122349569
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/clo_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ensembl_identifier_data_cleaned.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 31849231
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ensembl_identifier_data_cleaned.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ext_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 64227360
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ext_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/go_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 122488692
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/go_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/hp_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 84205700
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/hp_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/human_pro.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 217854250
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/human_pro.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/mondo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 231020989
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/mondo_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/node_metadata_dict.pkl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 325174359
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/node_metadata_dict.pkl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ontology_cleaning_report.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1436530
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ontology_cleaning_report.txt

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pr_with_imports.owl

- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 217870791
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pr_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pw_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4915785
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pw_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ro_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 857709
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ro_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/so_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4890370
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/so_with_imports.owl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/subclass_construction_map.pkl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 21922553
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/subclass_construction_map.pkl

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/vo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/01/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8388461
- GOOGLE_CLOUD_STORAGE_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/vo_with_imports.owl

Supplementary Document 3. edge_source_metadata.txt.

#Tue Nov 02 01:06:42 UTC 2021
#####

EDGE: chemical-disease

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt) | disease (./resources/processed_data/DISEASE_MONDO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[5]!="

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chemicals_diseases.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 701201197
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-disease_CTD_chemicals_diseases.tsv

EDGE: chemical-gene

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[6]==Homo sapiens | data[5].startswith('gene')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[9]affectsnot in x

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chem_gene_ixns.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 441097103
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-gene_CTD_chem_gene_ixns.tsv

EDGE: chemical-gobp

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Biological Process
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[8]<=1.04e-47

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 817733569
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-gobp_CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv

EDGE: chemical-gocc

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Cellular Component
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[8]<=1.04e-47

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 817733569
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-gocc_CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv

EDGE: chemical-gomf

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Molecular Function

- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[8]<=1.04e-47

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 817733569
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-gomf_CTD_chem_go_enriched.tsv

EDGE: chemical-pathway

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[5]==Homo sapiens
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ChEBI2Reactome_All_Levels.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 30485396
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-pathway_ChEBI2Reactome_All_Levels.txt

EDGE: chemical-phenotype

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt) | phenotype (./resources/processed_data/PHENOTYPE_HPO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[5]!="

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chemicals_diseases.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 701201197
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-phenotype_CTD_chemicals_diseases.tsv

EDGE: chemical-protein

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = chemical (./resources/processed_data/MESH_CHEBI_MAP.txt) | protein (./resources/processed_data/ENTREZ_GENE_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[6]==Homo sapiens | data[5].startswith('protein')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[9]affectsnot in x

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_chem_gene_ixns.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 441097103
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/chemical-protein_CTD_chem_gene_ixns.tsv

EDGE: disease-phenotype

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/phenotype.hpoa
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 27315334
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/disease-phenotype_phenotype.hpoa

EDGE: gene-disease

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = disease (./resources/processed_data/DISEASE_MONDO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[10]>=1.0

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/curated_gene_disease_associations.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11542996
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-disease_curated_gene_disease_associations.tsv

EDGE: gene-gene

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = gene (./resources/processed_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt) | gene (./resources/processed_data/ENSEMBL_GENE_ENTREZ_GENE_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/COMBINED.DEFAULT_NETWORKS.BP_COMBINING.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 246190113
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-gene_COMBINED.DEFAULT_NETWORKS.BP_COMBINING.txt

EDGE: gene-pathway

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3].startswith('REACT:R-HSA-')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/CTD_genes_pathways.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8192661
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-pathway_CTD_genes_pathways.tsv

EDGE: gene-phenotype

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = phenotype (./resources/processed_data/PHENOTYPE_HPO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[10]>=1.0

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/curated_gene_disease_associations.tsv
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11542996
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-phenotype_curated_gene_disease_associations.tsv

EDGE: gene-protein

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[4]==protein-coding
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENTREZ_GENE_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1124944
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-protein_ENTREZ_GENE_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

EDGE: gene-rna

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENTREZ_GENE_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 15146432
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gene-rna_ENTREZ_GENE_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt

EDGE: gobp-pathway

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==P | data[12]==taxon:9606 | data[5].startswith('REACTOME')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/gene_association.reactome
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11955743
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/gobp-pathway_gene_association.reactome

EDGE: pathway-gocc

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==C | data[12]==taxon:9606 | data[5].startswith('REACTOME')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/gene_association.reactome
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11955743
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/pathway-gocc_gene_association.reactome

EDGE: pathway-gomf

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==F | data[12]==taxon:9606 | data[5].startswith('REACTOME')
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/gene_association.reactome
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 11955743
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/pathway-gomf_gene_association.reactome

EDGE: protein-anatomy

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt) | anatomy (./resources/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Evidence at protein level | data[4]==anatomy
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20611429
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-anatomy_HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

EDGE: protein-catalyst

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_CATALYST.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 1639479
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-catalyst_UNIPROT_PROTEIN_CATALYST.txt

EDGE: protein-cell

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt) | cell (./resources/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Evidence at protein level | data[4]==cell line
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20611429
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-cell_HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

EDGE: protein-cofactor

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/UNIPROT_PROTEIN_COFACTOR.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 179314
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-cofactor_UNIPROT_PROTEIN_COFACTOR.txt

EDGE: protein-gobp

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==P | data[12]==taxon:9606
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/goa_human.gaf
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 109325311
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-gobp_goa_human.gaf

EDGE: protein-gocc

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==C | data[12]==taxon:9606
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/goa_human.gaf
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021

- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 109325311
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-gocc_goa_human.gaf

EDGE: protein-gomf

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[8]==F | data[12]==taxon:9606
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/goa_human.gaf
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 109325311
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-gomf_goa_human.gaf

EDGE: protein-pathway

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/UNIPROT_ACCESSION_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[5]==Homo sapiens
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/UniProt2Reactome_All_Levels.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 102191227
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-pathway_UniProt2Reactome_All_Levels.txt

EDGE: protein-protein

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = protein (./resources/processed_data/STRING_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt) | protein (./resources/processed_data/STRING_PRO_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[2]>=700

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/9606.protein.links.v11.0.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 540934917
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/protein-protein_9606.protein.links.v11.0.txt

EDGE: rna-anatomy

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = rna (./resources/processed_data/GENE_SYMBOL_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt) | anatomy (./resources/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Evidence at transcript level | data[4]==anatomy
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20611429
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/rna-anatomy_HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

EDGE: rna-cell

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = rna (./resources/processed_data/GENE_SYMBOL_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_MAP.txt) | cell (./resources/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_TISSUE_CELL_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[3]==Evidence at transcript level | data[4]==cell line
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 20611429
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/rna-cell_HPA_GTEX_RNA_GENE_PROTEIN_EDGES.txt

EDGE: rna-protein

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[4]==protein-coding
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_PROTEIN_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 2931638
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/rna-protein_ENSEMBL_TRANSCRIPT_PROTEIN_ONTOLOGY_MAP.txt

EDGE: variant-disease

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = disease (./resources/processed_data/DISEASE_MONDO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[9]!=-1 | data[16]==GRCh38 | data[8-9]dedupdesc
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[24] in ["criteria provided, multiple submitters, no conflicts", "reviewed by expert panel", "practice guideline"] | data[7]==1

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3662353455
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/variant-disease_CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt

EDGE: variant-gene

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[9]!=-1 | data[3]!=-1 | data[16]==GRCh38 | data[8-9]dedupdesc
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[24] in ["criteria provided, multiple submitters, no conflicts", "reviewed by expert panel", "practice guideline"]

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3662353455
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/variant-gene_CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt

EDGE: variant-phenotype

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = phenotype (./resources/processed_data/PHENOTYPE_HPO_MAP.txt)
- FILTERING CRITERIA = data[9]!=-1 | data[16]==GRCh38 | data[8-9]dedupdesc
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = data[24] in ["criteria provided, multiple submitters, no conflicts", "reviewed by expert panel", "practice guideline"] | data[7]==1

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 3662353455
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/edge_data/variant-phenotype_CLINVAR_VARIANT_GENE_DISEASE_PHENOTYPE_EDGES.txt

Supplementary Document 4. ontology_source_metadata.txt.

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#Tue Nov 02 01:05:41 UTC 2021
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EDGE: phenotype

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/hp_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 84205700
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/hp_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: go

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/go_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 122488692
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/go_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: disease

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/mondo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 231020989
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/mondo_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: vaccine

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/vo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 8388461
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/vo_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: chemical

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None

- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/chebi_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 643473711
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/chebi_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: anatomy

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ext_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 64227360
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/ext_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: cell

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/clo_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 122349569
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/clo_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: protein

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pr_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 217870791
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/pr_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: genomic

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/so_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4890370
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/so_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: pathway

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pw_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 4915785
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/pw_with_imports_with_imports.owl

EDGE: relation

DATA PROCESSING INFO

- IDENTIFIER MAPPING = None
- FILTERING CRITERIA = None
- EVIDENCE CRITERIA = None

DATA INFO

- DOWNLOAD_URL = https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ro_with_imports.owl
- DOWNLOAD_DATE = 11/02/2021
- FILE_SIZE_IN_BYTES = 857709
- DOWNLOADED_FILE_LOCATION = resources/ontologies/ro_with_imports_with_imports.owl

Supplementary Document 5. ontology_cleaning_report.txt.

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ONTOLOGY CLEANING REPORT
Mon Nov 01 09:57:17 UTC 2021

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ONTOLOGY: chebi_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/chebi_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/chebi_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 5644239 Triples; 168627 Classes; 0 Individuals; 10 Object Properties; 37 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 5569987 Triples; 150080 Classes; 0 Individuals; 10 Object Properties; 37 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 18547
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0
 - Object Properties: 0

ONTOLOGY: clo_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/clo_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/clo_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 1387096 Triples; 111712 Classes; 41 Individuals; 116 Object Properties; 192 Annotation Properties; 7 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 1422153 Triples; 111696 Classes; 33 Individuals; 112 Object Properties; 187 Annotation Properties; 7 Connected Components
- Value Errors (n=1):
 - RDF/XML parsing error in file builds/temp/clo_with_imports.owl, line 10971, column 99.
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 2
- Obsolete Classes: 13
- Punning Errors:
 - Classes (n=10):
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000062
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001017
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001004
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000926
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000029
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001009
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CLO_0054407
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0000383
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CLO_0054409
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/UBERON_0001555
 - Object Properties (n=6):
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002222
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000062
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/BFO_0000063
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002161
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002091
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000087

ONTOLOGY: ext_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ext_with_imports.owl

- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ext_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 769010 Triples; 28166 Classes; 0 Individuals; 239 Object Properties; 282 Annotation Properties; 19 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 750999 Triples; 26577 Classes; 0 Individuals; 239 Object Properties; 282 Annotation Properties; 19 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 1589
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: go_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/go_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/go_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 1425011 Triples; 62437 Classes; 0 Individuals; 9 Object Properties; 55 Annotation Properties; 2 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 1334338 Triples; 55556 Classes; 0 Individuals; 9 Object Properties; 55 Annotation Properties; 2 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 6881
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: hp_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/hp_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/hp_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 934712 Triples; 41442 Classes; 0 Individuals; 256 Object Properties; 226 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 934877 Triples; 41125 Classes; 0 Individuals; 256 Object Properties; 226 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 313
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: mondo_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/mondo_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/mondo_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 2375692 Triples; 58553 Classes; 18 Individuals; 339 Object Properties; 153 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 2336440 Triples; 55929 Classes; 17 Individuals; 338 Object Properties; 153 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 2622
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: pr_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pr_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pr_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 2078128 Triples; 148164 Classes; 0 Individuals; 12 Object Properties; 11 Annotation Properties; 3 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 2078128 Triples; 148164 Classes; 0 Individuals; 12 Object Properties; 11 Annotation Properties; 3 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0

- Deprecated Classes: 0
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: pw_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/pw_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/pw_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 35291 Triples; 2642 Classes; 0 Individuals; 1 Object Properties; 19 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 34901 Triples; 2600 Classes; 0 Individuals; 1 Object Properties; 19 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 42
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: ro_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/ro_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/ro_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 8069 Triples; 99 Classes; 5 Individuals; 611 Object Properties; 113 Annotation Properties; 3 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 7971 Triples; 99 Classes; 5 Individuals; 599 Object Properties; 113 Annotation Properties; 3 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 12
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: so_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/so_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/so_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 44890 Triples; 2925 Classes; 0 Individuals; 50 Object Properties; 41 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 42198 Triples; 2583 Classes; 0 Individuals; 50 Object Properties; 41 Annotation Properties; 1 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors: 0
- Deprecated Classes: 342
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: vo_with_imports.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/vo_with_imports.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/vo_with_imports.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 88373 Triples; 7198 Classes; 167 Individuals; 232 Object Properties; 99 Annotation Properties; 5 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 91683 Triples; 7194 Classes; 167 Individuals; 232 Object Properties; 99 Annotation Properties; 5 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors (n=2):
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PRO_000000001
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PRO_000015399
- Deprecated Classes: 0
- Obsolete Classes: 0
- Punning Errors: 0

ONTOLOGY: PheKnowLator_MergedOntologies.owl

- Original GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/original_data/PheKnowLator_MergedOntologies.owl
- Processed GCS URL: https://storage.googleapis.com/pheknowlator/archived_builds/release_v3.0.2/build_01NOV2021/data/processed_data/PheKnowLator_MergedOntologies.owl
- Statistics Before Cleaning: 13934582 Triples; 562412 Classes; 197 Individuals; 853 Object Properties; 635 Annotation Properties; 8 Connected Components
- Statistics After Cleaning: 13935691 Triples; 558715 Classes; 190 Individuals; 852 Object Properties; 635 Annotation Properties; 8 Connected Components
- Value Errors: 0
- Identifier Errors (n=2):
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PRO_000000001
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/PRO_000015399
- Punning Errors:
 - Classes (n=8):
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_147099
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_6040
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CLO_0054409
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_6157
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_6073
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_41324
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_8570
 - http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCBITaxon_110815
 - Object Properties: 0
- Normalization:
 - Normalized Entities (n=7):
 - OGG_0000000002 rdfs:subClassOf SO_0000704
 - PR_000000001 rdfs:subClassOf SO_0000104
 - CHEBI_36080 rdfs:subClassOf SO_0000104
 - OGMS_0000045 rdfs:subClassOf MONDO_0000001
 - OBI_1110034 rdfs:subClassOf CHEBI_59132
 - VO_0003030 rdfs:subClassOf CHEBI_5291
 - FMA_12278 rdfs:subClassOf CHEBI_24621
 - Normalized HGNC IDs: 23631
 - Other Classes that May Need Normalizing: 404495
 - Deprecated Ontology HGNC Identifiers Needing Alignment: 0

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Supplementary Document 7. pkt_build_log.log (Knowledge Graph Construction).

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{"asctime": "2021-11-02 05:13:24,844", "levelname": "INFO", "name": "pkt_kg.knowledge_graph", "module": "knowledge_graph", "funcName": "creates_new_edges", "lineno": 347, "message": "Created CHEMICAL-GOMF (class-class) Edges: 164592 OWL Edges, 27209 Original Edges; 55759 OWL Nodes, Original Nodes: 1133 chemical(s), 204 gomf(s)"}

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http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002436:1001470, http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0001025:689237, http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0002200:428381, http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/RO_0000056:381743, density: 3.427532965137278e-07, 2 component(s): {0: 8644227, 1: 3 nodes: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Ontology> | <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/chebi/204/chebi.owl> | <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/chebi.owl>}
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{"asctime": "2021-11-02 09:58:07,196", "levelname": "INFO", "name": "pkt_kg.knowledge_graph", "module": "knowledge_graph", "funcName": "construct_knowledge_graph", "lineno": 604, "message": "**** Writing Knowledge Graph Edge Lists ****"}
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